

Cold tolerance

A method for testing cold tolerance of rice at early seedling stage

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Non-germination of seeds at low temperature is not a serious problem in rice culture even in low-temperature areas, unless rice is direct seeded. The farmer ordinarily soaks and incubates the rice seeds in a warm place so that it is the growth of the pregerminated seeds when broadcast in the nursery bed or main field that is affected by the low temperature. Rice farmers in China often broadcast pregerminated seeds when the temperature fluctuates around 8°C. Such low temperature either kills the pregerminated seeds or retard their growth. Cold tolerance at this stage is necessary.

This report describes the method that was developed for testing cold tolerance — the ability to maintain cellular integrity at low temperature and resume active growth when temperatures subsequently increase — at the early seedling stage. This method was used in screening 700 rice varieties from China.

1. Soak around 50 uniform seeds per variety for 24 hours in ordinary glass bottles.

2. Drain the water, wash the seeds thoroughly using sterile water during the last washing if possible. Cover the seeds with moist tissue paper.

3. Incubate the seeds for 3 days at room temperature, remove the tissue paper, add water to submerge the germinated seeds to a 3-cm depth, and place in the refrigerator (4°C) for 10 days.

4. Remove the bottles from the refrigerator and keep in a warm room for a day before placing under full sunlight. Score the entries 10 days after removal from the refrigerator.

Table 1. Cold tolerance score of 691 Chinese varieties at early seedling stage. IRRI, 1980.

Score	Indica		Sinica		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
1	10	2	74	35	84	12
3	15	3	49	23	64	9
5	30	6	30	14	60	9
7	121	25	36	17	157	23
9	303	64	23	11	326	47
Total	479	100	212	100	691	100

The criteria for scoring at early seedling stage are as follows:

Score	Description
1	All seeds germinated, seedlings with green leaves.
3	Less than 30% of the seedlings are dead.
5	30 to 50% of the seedlings dead.
7	Over 50% dead seedlings.
9	100% dead seedlings.

Table 2. Indica varieties with a score of 1 at early seedling stage and their score for seedling vigor. IRRI, 1980.

Accession no.	Variety	Seedling vigor
01140	Chang jo	1
01145	Chiu Chiu ku	3
01179	Hung Chao Lu Yu	3
01198	Yang Ku Tsi	3
01226	Ti Ho Hung	1
01240	PI 160639	1
01261	PI 160662	5
01518	PI 160968-2	5
01597	96-48-1	1
01599	97-51-2	1

While scoring for cold tolerance, one can score for seedling vigor in this test. The scoring criteria for seedling vigor follow:

Score	Description
1	Seedling height exceeds the height of the bottles (10 cm).
3	Seedling height is 8-10 cm.
5	Seedling height is 5-7 cm.
7	Seedling height is 3-4 cm.
9	Seedling height is less than 1 cm.

Table 1 shows the number of indica and sinica entries and their score at early seedling stage. A score of 1 was obtained by 2% of the indica varieties and 35% of the sinica. The indica varieties with a score of 1 are listed in Table 2; the sinica varieties are in Table 3.

In the development of this testing method, different number of days of incubation were tried and 3 days was found optimum. The amount of water added to the seeds at low temperature did not matter much; no significant

Table 3. Sinica varieties with a score of 1 for early seedling stage and seedling vigor.

Accession no.	Variety	Accession no.	Variety
01045	Yen Tiao Hsien	01278	PI 160677-5
01120	Marratilli	01304	Shen Li Ping Hsing
01220	PI 160615	01305	Chiang Li 3
01244	PI 160643	01323	AI Chih Hsu
01245	Pao Tswan	01337	Yen Fang Chu 1
01247	San Pao	01338	Yen Fang Chu 1
01249	Moh Tsu Ju	01342	Pai Mang Jh Pen
01250	Shih Chien	01472	Chung Ta 312/Binastian
01251	I 24-255 Chiu Tien	01485	AI Yen Lu
01255	Hsin Nung Ju	01612	Ta Hai
01273	AI Kwoh 4	01616	Bassetze
01277	PI 160677-4	03502	CI 7739

difference in results was obtained.

Although there was a significant positive correlation ($r^2 = 0.439^{**}$)

between cold tolerance at early seedling stage and seedling stage (10 to 30 days after sowing), the low correlation

warrants the two different screenings for elite lines or varieties and possible donor varieties. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Widespread occurrence of sheath rot in Bihar

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Sheath rot of rice caused by *Acrocladium oryzae* (revised as *Sarocladium oryzae*) was observed in Bihar for the first time during kharif 1977 at ARI, Mithapur, in national screening nursery (NSN) and International Rice Yield Nursery (IRYN) trials.

In the 1979 kharif, sheath rot was reported at the RAU Regional Research Institutes at Sabour, Bhagalpur; Dholi, Muzaffarpur; Kanke, Ranchi; and Mithapur, Patna. The symptoms are limited to complete discoloration of the

ultimate leaf sheath, a high proportion of unfilled grains, grain discoloration, and choking of panicles. ■

Effect of some fungicides on the control of narrow brown leaf spot of rice

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Narrow brown leaf spot of rice caused by *Cercospora oryzae* occurs in severe proportion during samba (Aug-Jan) and thaladi (Oct-Feb) seasons. A pot culture experiment during 1979 thaladi studied fungicides for controlling the disease. The rice variety IR20, which is susceptible to narrow brown leaf spot, was raised in concrete pots. The test fungicides — carbendazim, carboxin, zineb, edifenphos, and Cuman L at 0.2%

were sprayed on the rice plants twice at 10-day intervals at maximum tillering. The natural occurrence of the disease was rated according to the 1975 Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

Foliar spray with fungicides significantly reduced the narrow brown leaf spot. Among the fungicides, carbendazim was the most effective, followed by carboxin (see table). ■

Fungicides for control of narrow brown leaf spot of rice. Tamil Nadu, India.

Fungicide	Mean disease incidence (%)
Carbendazim	5.2
Carboxin	8.7
Zineb	10.5
Edifenphos	13.8
Cuman L	28.3
Untreated control	39.3

Influence of neem cake and coal-tar-coated urea on bacterial blight of rice

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A glasshouse experiment investigated the effect of slow-release nitrogenous fertilizers, such as neem cake + coal tar and coal-tar-coated urea, on the incidence of bacterial blight of rice on Taichung Native 1.

Two levels of nitrogen — 100 and 200 kg N/ha — were applied separately as basal and 3 split doses. In the split application, 25% was applied at transplanting, 50% at maximum tillering, and 25% at the time of inoculation. Sixty-day-old plants were clip-inoculated with a virulent strain of *Xanthomonas oryzae*. The lesion length, plant height, and tiller numbers were recorded 14 days after inoculation.

There were 13 treatments in the experiment, including uncoated urea and the control.

The results indicated that disease incidence, plant height, and tiller number were maximum in treatments with 200 kg N and neem cake and coal tar and

were lowest in the control. There is evidence that slow release of nitrogen as urea or neem cake or coal-tar treated urea increased lesion length.

Field trials are in progress to confirm the study and yield in different treatments. ■

Effect of the application of neem cake + coal tar and coal-tar-coated urea on bacterial blight incidence, plant height, and tiller number of rice plants. Andhra Pradesh, India.

Treatment	Application time	Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Lesion length (cm)	Plant ht (cm)	Tiller no.
Uncoated urea	Basal	100	5.4	75.6	5.3
Uncoated urea	Split	100	8.5	80.6	4.7
Uncoated urea	Basal	200	6.1	78.4	5.8
Uncoated urea	Split	200	9.6	83.2	7.2
Neem cake + coal-tar-coated urea	Basal	100	6.3	77.5	5.0
Neem cake + coal-tar-coated urea	Split	100	10.6	83.1	5.8
Neem cake + coal-tar-coated urea	Basal	200	8.3	84.2	8.1
Neem cake + coal-tar-coated urea	Split	200	10.9	88.2	8.7
Coal-tar-coated urea	Basal	100	10.1	82.1	5.3
Coal-tar-coated urea	Split	100	8.4	80.6	5.8
Coal-tar-coated urea	Basal	200	10.2	86.4	9.8
Coal-tar-coated urea	Split	200	8.8	81.1	6.8
Control		0	5.2	71.0	3.5